

CRITICAL REVIEW ON YAVA KSHAARA W.S.R to Khasara Kalpana

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ABSTRACT

Kshaara (Alkali) has been in existence from ancient time. Their importance lies in the fact that they can be utilized to replace certain surgical procedures. It is derived from plant, animal and mineral sources. Many *kshaara* have been described in our texts. Among them *Yava Kshaara* is mentioned in *Kshaaradvaya*, *Kshaaratrya*, *Kshaara Panchaka*, *Kshaara Saptaka*, *Kshaara Ashtaka*. It is prepared from the plant *Yava*, *Yava* consists of dried whole plant of *Hordeum Vulgare* Linn. (*Fam.Poaceae*). It is alkaline preparation made with the ingredient of *Yava* Ash and water. It is consist of *Katu Rasa*, *Laghu*, *Snigdha*, *Sukshma*, *Sara Guna*, *Ushna Veerya*, *Katu Veepaka Vatanashaka*, *Kaphahara Deepena*, *Pachana*, *Lekhana*, *Swedapravartaka*, *Mutrala*, *Shothaghna* properties. It is widely used in diseases condition like *Bastishoola*, *Gulma Mutrkrichha*, *Shoola*, *Kaasa*, *Shwaasa Murtaghaata* etc. In this article critical review on *Kshaara Kalpana* and *Yava Kshaara* from available Ayurvedic classical texts and respective standard scientific journals are done.

KEYWORDS: *Kshaara Kalpana*, *Kshaara*, *Yava Kshaara*.

INTRODUCTION

Kshaara has been known nearly from the period of 500 years before.^[1] Although nothing has been mentioned in vedic literature, the name of *Kshaara* reflects in the *Upnishada* for the first time. Samhita period has described *Kshaara* elaborately. Acharya Charaka has defined *Kshaara* and given its types, properties and various applications of them.^[2] Acharya Sushruta has dedicated a separate chapter in Sutrasthana on *Kshaara*.^[3] Ashtanga Hridaya and Ashtanga Sangraha.^[4] Sharngdhara Samhita,^[5] and Yogrtanakara^[6] have all mentioned *Kshaara*. *Kalpna* Rasa Ratna Samuchya, Rasa Trangini nearly all RasaShastra texts and modern texts have mentioned *Kshaara Kalpana*. *Kshaara* is widely used in *Udararoga*, *Gulama*, disorders of *Yakrita* – *Pleeha* *Mutrkrichha*, *Mutraghata*, *Ashmari*, *Bhagandhara*, *Arsha*, *Arbuda*, *Naadivrana*, *Kushtha*, and also helps to cure *Kandu*, *Kleda*, *Putikarana*, *Shoola*, *Krimikarana*

Critical Review on *Kshaara Kalpna*

Etymology

According Shabda Kalpdruma^[7]

Kshaara was derived from “क्षर्” *Dhatu* which means movement.

According to Vachaspatyam^[8]

क्षर स्पन्दने क्षण हिंसाया तत्रद क्षारः

क्षार बली क्षारतोति क्षारः (Vachaspatyama 3/ Pg 2376)

The word *Kshaara* means *Spandana*, *Hinsa* and *Ksharana*. The later *Kshaara* gives the meaning of violence hence; it destroys skin, tissues etc. from the body by cutting or damaging them.

According to Acharya Charaka

क्षरणात् क्षारः नासौ रसः द्रव्यं तदनेकरस

समुत्पन्नमनेकरसं कटुकलवण पुयिष्टमने

केन्द्रियार्थ समन्वितं करणाभिनिवृत्तम् ॥ (*Ch.Su.26/9*)

Because of its corrosive nature (*Ksharana*) it is known as *Kshaara* (Alkali) *Kshaara* did not have any of the *Rasa* but it has combination of *Rasa* mainly *Katu & Lavana Rasa*. It is object of many senses and it involves specific method of preparation.^[9]

छित्वा छित्वा आशयात् क्षारः क्षरत्वात् क्षारयत्यअघः ।
(*Ch.Chi.* 5/58)

Acharya Charaka has mentioned efficacy of *Kshaara* under the context of *Gulma Chikitsa*. It has the property of *Ksharana*, so it gradually erodes *Kaphaja Gulma* and brings it downwards.^[10]

According Acharya Sushruta

तत्र क्षरणात् क्षणनाच्चा क्षारः ॥ (*Su.Su.*1/4)

The substance is called *Kshaara*, because it causes *Ksharana* to *Mamsa* etc. *Dhatu*.^[11]

Definitions

- The substance which expels out the 'Dusta *Tvakmasadi*' by its *Ksharana* action is called *Kshaara*.^[12]
- According to Dalhana, the substance which helps in *Shodhana* of *Dosha*, *Dhatu*, *Mala* of body because of its *Ksharana* action is called *Kshaara*.^[13]
- According AFI, *Kshaara* are alkaline substances obtained from the ash of drugs.^[14]

Historical review on *Kshaara Kalpana Samhitakala*

Description of *kshaara* is mentioned in detail with its therapeutic utility in *Samhitakala*

Charaka Samhita

Acharya Charaka has dealt with definition, varieties, properties, application of *Kshaara*.^[15] which was mentioned in **Table 1**.

Table 1: Showing different *Kshaara* mentioned in Charaka Samhita.

Sr. no.	Name of <i>Kshaara</i>	References
1	<i>Agnimantha Kshaara</i>	<i>Ch. Chi.</i> 13/170-171
2	<i>Apamarga Kshaara</i>	<i>Ch. Chi.</i> 13/170-171
3	<i>Dashmoola Kshaara</i>	<i>Ch. Chi.</i> 13/169-170
4	<i>Aja pureesha Kshaara</i>	<i>Ch. Chi.</i> 13/162-165
5	<i>Asana Kshaara</i>	<i>Ch. Chi.</i> 4/94
6	<i>Ingudi Kshaara</i>	<i>Ch. Chi.</i> 18/171
7	<i>Kadali Kshaara</i>	<i>Ch. Chi.</i> 1(3)/15-23
8	<i>Ashvgandha Kshaara</i>	<i>Ch. Chi.</i> 17/117
9	<i>Eranda patra Kshaara</i>	<i>Ch. Chi.</i> 5/178
10	<i>Yava Kshaara</i>	<i>Ch. Chi.</i> 5/147

Sushruta Samhita

Definition, properties, types, method of preparation and plants used for *Kshaara*, *Guna*, *Dosha*, *Rasapanchaka*, Indication, Contraindication and their treatments are described in details with preparation of *Mridu*, *Madhyama*, *Tikshana Kshaara* and its specific indication

in *Sutrasthana Adhyaya* no. 11 named *Kshaarapakavidhi* by Acharya Sushruta.^[16,17] It shows tremendous effect in *Shalyatantra* due to its *Chedana*, *Bhedana*, *Lekhana* property.^[18] Degenerated *Dhatu* and unhealthy tissues removed from vitiated location because of its *Ksharana* effects of *Kshaara*.^[19]

Ashtanga Samgrha and Ashtanga Hridaya

General properties, *Dosha* and action of *Kshaara* with different formulation which is made up from *Kshaara* have been mentioned by both treaties in 4th – 5th Century. *Pratisarniya Kshaara* is indicated in *Arbuda*, *Bhagandara*, *Grahani*, *Shvitra*, *Naadivrana*, *Kushtha* etc. and *Paniya Kshaara* is indicated in *Arsha*, *Bhagandara*, *Ashmari*, *Udararoga*, *Garavisha* in *Ashtanga Hridaya*.^[20] It is contraindicated in person who are weak, *Vata-Pitta* disorders, *Jvara*, *Atisaara*, *Paanduroga*, *Prameha*, less flesh on the body because of its complication.^[21]

Chakradatta

Chakrapani has mentioned *Kshaara Sandhanvidhi*, preparation of *Pratisaarniya Kshaara*^[22], preparation of *Paaniya Kshaara*^[23], preparation of *Kshaarasutra* with application and indications of *Pratisarniya Kshaara* in 11th century.^[24] In *Mutrkrichha Chikitsa*, *Yava Kshaara* is mixed with sugar or *Kantakaari Svarasa* and *Madhu*.^[25] In treatment of *Ashmari*, *Kshaara* are taken along with *Vataghnadravya*.^[26]

Sharangadhara Samhita

Kshaara is to be prepared in mud pot and it is used as *Pratisaarniya* (Externally) and *Peya* (Internally) along with suitable *Anupana* by Acharya Sharangadhara in the 14th century.^[27] Beside this *Kshaara* (*Yava Kshaara*) is used in many formulations which reduce the symptoms of *Udararoga*, *Gulma*, disorders of *Yakrita –Pleeha*.^[28]

Gadanigraha

Kshaara is beneficial in many disease condition like *Apaamaarga Kshaarataila* in *Badharya*^[29] and *Apaamaarga Kshaara* along with other ingredient in *Bhagandhara* by Acharya Shodhala.^[30]

Yogaratanakara

Various method of preparation of *Kshaara* along with mixing of *Pippali Churna* in treatment of *Pleehodara* in 18th Century.^[31]

Bhava Prakasha

Name of *Kshaaraashaka* and *Guna* of *Yava Kshaara*, *Svarjika Kshaara* and *Tankana Kshaara* were mentioned by Acharya Bhavamishra.

Rasatantra Kala

There is no separate chapter on *Kshaara Kalpana* is mentioned in *Rasa Grantha* except *Rasatarangini*.^[32] *Kshaara Dravya* are used in *Deepana Samskara* of *Parada*^[33] and *Shodhana*, *Marana* of *Dhatu*^[34] are mentioned in various *Rasa Grantha*.

Rasa Ratna Samuchchya

Under following *Paribhaashaa*^[35] i.e.

Kshaara Traya – *Kshaara* of *Yava*, *Svarjika*, *Tankana* is mentioned

Kshaara Panchaka – *Kshaara* of *Palaasha*, *Mushaka*, *Yava*, *Tilnala*, *Suvarchika* is mentioned.

Rasendra Chintaamani

In 9th chapter of Rasendra Chintaamani, *Kshaara Gutika* is explained which contains *Kshaaradvaya* (*Yava Kshaara* and *Sarjika Kshaara*). (5-9 Shotharogadhikaara).^[36]

Ayurveda Prakasha

Method of preparation of *Kshaara* is mentioned.^[37]

Rasatarangini

Method of preparation of *Kshaara* properties indication and dose along with description of *Apaamaarga Kshaara* introduction, properties, method of preparation dose, indication along with description of *Yava Kshaara*, *Sarjikshaara*, *Tanakana Kshaara* are mentioned.^[38]

Dravyaguna Vigyana

Acharya Yadavji Trikamaji has described method of preparation of *Kshaara* in his text *Dravyaguna Vigyana*.^[39]

Ayurvedic Formulary of India (AFI): A separate chapter of *Lavana – Kshaara* has been mentioned in AFI Part -1, 10th Chapter. different formulation of *Kshaara* with references, dose, *Anupaana* with its therapeutic indication etc. are mentioned in this book.^[40]

Drug and cosmetic Act 1940 and Rule 1945^[41]

List of machinery, equipment and minimum manufacturing premises required for the manufacturer of *Kshaara* is mentioned in this Act.

Importance of Kshaara

External and internal uses of *Kshaara* are mentioned according to disease condition of body in classics. It is having *Ushana*, *Tikshana*, *Paachana*, *Vilayana*, *Ropana*, *Shoshana*, *Stambhana* and *Lekhana* etc. qualities. Because of these qualities it shows tremendous results in various disease condition but it can't be used in children, old age, weak and delicate person due to its adverse effects.^[42]

Methods of Preparation of *Kshaara* which was mentioned in Table 2.

Table 2: Showing method of preparation of *Kshaara* mentioned in various texts.

Sr. no.	References	Ratio of ash and water	Duration of soaking	Filtration method
1	Sushruta Samhita Su. 11/13	1:6	Over night	21 times
2	Sharangadhara Samhita Ma. Kha. 11/101-103	1:4	Overnight in earthen vessel	Filtered through cloth
3	Rasatarangini 14/59-61	1:4	3hs	Filtered with 3 folded cloth
4	Ayurveda Saarasamgraha Pg.no.609	1:8	2-3 days in earthen vessel or steel vessel	Filtered 7 times with 4 folded cloth
5	Chakradatta Arsha Roga Pg. no. 66	1:4	-	-

Classification of *Kshaaraa*^[43,44,45,46,47,48]

Rasapanchaka of Kshaara^[49]

Rasa : Amla varjiita sarva rasa (Pradhana Rasa Katurasa, Anurasa – Lavana)
Guna : Teekshana

Virya: Ushana

Vipaka : Katu

Kshaara Guna and Dosha which was mentioned in **Table 3.**

Table 3: Showing Kshaara Guna and Kshaara Dosha.

Sr. no.	Guna	References		Dosha	References	
		Su.Su . 11/16	A.H.Su. 30/2		Su.Su. 11/17	A.S. Su. 36/6
1	Nati- teekshna	+	+	Ati mridu	+	+
2	Nati- mridu	+	+	Ati sveta	+	+
3	Nati – shukla	+	+	Ati usnata	+	+
4	Slakshnatva	+	+	Ati tikshnta	+	+
5	Picchila	+	+	Ati picchila	+	+
6	Avishyanda	+	+	Ati visarpita	+	+
7	Shighrakaratva	+	+	Ati sandrata	+	+
8	Shiva	+	-	Ati tanu	-	+
9	Shikhari	-	+	Apakvata	+	+
10	Sukha nirvapyta	-	+	Hina drvyata	+	+

+ = available in classics

- = is not available in classics

Critical Review on Yava Kshaara

Background

Ayurveda deals with minerals, metals, and herbs in therapeutics that have been classified into several groups. Among them *Yava Kshaara* is prepared from the plant *Yava*, *Yava* consists of dried whole plant of *Hordeum Vulgare* Linn. (*Fam. Poaceae*). It is counted in *Kshaaraadvaya*, *Kshaaratraya*, *Kshaara Panchaka*, *Kshaara Saptaka*, *Kshaara Ashtaka*. It is used as an important ingredient in many formulations mentioned in various classical texts.

Source

Yava Kshaara is prepared from the plant *Yava*. *Yava* consists of dried whole plant of *Hordeum Vulgare* Linn. (*Fam. Poaceae*).^[50] It is alkaline preparation made with

the ingredient of *yava asha* and water.^[51,52] It is found in all three kingdoms of nature. In the **Vegetable kingdom** it is found either as carbonate of potash or as potash in combination with organic acid. Plant absorb it from soil and when incinerated their ashes give *Yava Kshaara*. Succulent plant contains a large proportion of it than woody parts. “Impure potassium carbonate” has been known from very ancient time. its principle source in India is wood ashes because potash is an indispensable element for the growth of most plants. In **Mineral kingdom** it is obtained from rocks where it exists as sulphate, nitrates, carbonates and silicates. It is also found in feldspar of granite. It is an ingredient of various mineral water. In **Animal kingdom** it is an essential constituent. it is found in the milk, flesh and urine of person who take citrate or tartrate of potassium.^[53]

Vernacular Name^[54]

Sanskrit	Paakya, Kshaara, Yavakshaara, Darulawana, Yavaagraja
Hindi	Javakhar, Javaakhar, Khar
English	Carbonate of potash, Potash carbonate, Potash, Salt of tartar
Gujarati	Javakhara, Kharo
Latin	Potasil carbonas

Synonyms^[55]

Yava Kshaara, *Yavaptya*, *Yavaja*, *Yavashukaja*, *Yavya*, *Yavaagraja*, *Yavanaalaja*, *Yavashuka*, *Shookaja*, *Paakya*, etc.

Yava Kshaara it is good for digestion. It subsides *vata-kaphanaashaka*, *anaha*, *grhanai*, *paadu*, *gulama*, *pleeha*, *hridaamaroga*, *shookranaashana*.^[57,58]

Rasa Panchaka^[56]

Rasa: Katu

Guna: Laghu, Snigdha, Sukshma, Sara

Veerya: Ushna

Veepaka: Katu

Doshaghnta: Vatanashaka, Kaphahara

Karma: Deepena, Pachana, lekhanam, Swedapravartaka, Mutrala, Shothaghnta

Physical Properties of Yava Kshaara

Nature – Amorphous

Colour – Creamish white

Taste – Salty

Solubility – Completely soluble in water producing strong alkali solution

Chemical Formula – K₂CO₃ (Potassium Carbonate)

Important formulation

Shothaari Lauha, Agnitundai Vati, Arshkuthaara Rasa, Chandraprabhaa Vati, Grahani Kapaata Rasa, Chitrkadi vati, Kshara Taila, Pipaalayadi Churna, Marichyadi Vti, Kankayana Vati, Narayana Churna etc.

Yava Kshaara Amayika Prayoga^[59]

- **To Increase Appetite** – Yava Kshaara is mixed with *Trikatu Churna* and *Jeeraka Churna*
- **In Bastishoola** - Yava Kshaara is mixed with *Marich Churna* and *Shunthi Churna* taken with luke warm water in twice or thrice a day
- **In Ashamari and Mutrakrichha** - Yava Kshaara is taken along with *Takra*
- **In Gulma, Shoola, Hridroga, Kaasa, Shwaasa** – Yava Kshaara, *Saindhava, Dashmoola Kashaya*
- **In Murtaghaata and Shukraashmari** - Yava Kshaara, *Kushmanda Swarasa, Guda*

CONCLUSION

In our classical texts detail description about *Kshaara Kalapna* is mentioned like, Etymology, Definition, *Guna* – *Karma, Rasapanchaka*, method of preparation, classification and importance of *Kshaara*. Detail review on *Yava Kshaara* is also reviewed like, Sources, *Rasapanchaka*, Synonym, Physical property and Therapeutic activity. *Yava Kshaara* consist of *Katu Rasa, Laghu, Snigdha, Sukshma, Sara Guna, Ushna Veerya, Katu Veepaka Vatanashaka, Kaphahara, Deepena, Pachana, Lekhana, Swedapravartaka, Mutrala, Shothaghna* properties. Hence it can be concluded that based on properties and therapeutic action of *Kshaara*, it can be used internally as well as externally to cure various diseases. *Yava Kshaara* is good for digestion. It subsides *Vata-Kaphanaashaka, Anaha, Grhanai, Paadu, Gulma, Pleeha, Hridaamaroga, Shookranaashana, Bastishoola, Asmari, Mutrakruccha, Mutrghata* etc disorders. by using it with appropriate *Anupana*.

List of abbreviation

Su.Su - Sushruta Sutrasthana; A.H.Su.- Ashtanga Hridaya Sutrasthana, A.S.Su- Ashtanga Sangraha Sutrasthana.

Conflict of interest: Not any.

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 58. Bhudev Mukerji, English translation, Rasa Jala Nidhi or Ocean of Indian Chemistry and Alchemy, Vol -111, Chapter -5, 189-190.
 59. Acharya Sadanand Sharma, Rasatarangini, Pandit Kashinathashastri, Taranga 13/10-32, Chukhambha Sanskrit Bhavana, Vranasi, Reprint, 2014.